

Electrochemical reactions at sacrificial electrodes. Part XVI : Synthesis of zinc thiolates/dithiolates and their coordination compounds

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Manuscript received 4 June 2004, revised 7 March 2005, accepted 8 March 2005

Electrochemical reactions of various thiols and dithiols have been carried out at sacrificial zinc anode and inert platinum cathode using tetrabutylammonium chloride as supporting electrolyte and acetonitrile as solvent. Solid products separated in the anode compartment have been identified as zinc thiolates and zinc dithiolates. The coordination compounds of these thiolates and dithiolates with 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridine have also been synthesized electrochemically. The solid products separated in anode compartment were isolated and identified by elemental analysis and infrared spectral data. The current efficiencies of these systems have also been determined which are very high.

Electrochemical technique has widely been used in synthetic organic and inorganic chemistry¹⁻³. The most important advantages of this technique are the simplicity and high product yield⁴. In continuation to our interest in the electrochemical synthesis of inorganic compounds⁴⁻⁸, we report in this communication the synthesis of zinc thiolates and dithiolates and their coordination compounds.

Experimental

Reagents and solvent : Acetonitrile was dried over phosphorous pentoxide, then twice distilled and was used as solvent. Tetrabutylammonium chloride was crystallised from conductivity water, dried under reduced pressure at 100°C and was used as supporting electrolyte in these systems. Thiophenol and butane-1-thiol (RSH), butane-1,4-dithiol and hexane-1,6-dithiol (HS(CH₂)_nSH) were used as supplied.

Procedure and technique : Reactions were carried out in H-type cell made of Pyrex glass having anode and cathode compartments separated from each other by a sintered glass disc of G-3 porosity. Platinum foil (1 × 1 cm²) and zinc plate (2 × 10 × 2 cm³) were used as cathode and anode respectively. Both the outlets of H-type cell were fitted with guard tubes and were sealed in order to protect the product from direct contact with air and moisture.

The reaction mixture containing 2 g of thiol or dithiol, tetrabutylammonium chloride (0.5 g) in 250 ml of acetonitrile was taken in the H-type cell. It was connected with the direct current power supply and the potential across the electrodes was so adjusted that a current of 20 mA passed

through the cell. The electrolysis was conducted for 8 h with continuous stirring. The cell is represented as :

where Zn₍₊₎ is sacrificial zinc anode and Pt₍₋₎ is inert platinum cathode.

The solid product separated in anode compartment was filtered, washed repeatedly with acetonitrile and dry ether and then dried in vacuum.

The coordination compounds of these products of thiols and dithiols were prepared in the similar way except that 1 g of the ligand (1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl) was also added in addition to other substrates before starting electrolysis.

Elemental analysis : The products were analysed for zinc contents. Weighed amount of the product was heated to dry mass with fuming nitric acid three times. The dry mass was dissolved in few drops of dilute hydrochloric acid and 100 mL solution was made. The contents of zinc in solution were estimated volumetrically by oxine method⁹. The microanalysis of C, H of these compounds have also been carried out.

Infrared spectra of these products were recorded with Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in the region of 4000–450 cm⁻¹ using potassium bromide pellets and in the region of 450–250 cm⁻¹ using polythene plates.

Melting point of the products was determined by using

electrical device. Current efficiencies of most of these systems were also determined by electrolysis of the solutions of various systems at a constant current of 20 mA for three hours in the H-type cell. The solution obtained after electrolysis was first distilled and then dried on film evaporator under reduced pressure. The zinc contents in dry mass were estimated volumetrically as discussed above⁹.

Experimentally determined zinc contents in the electrolysed solution

$$\text{Current efficiency} = \frac{\text{Experimentally determined zinc contents in the electrolysed solution}}{\text{Theoretical zinc dissolved when a current of 20 mA is passed through solution for three hours}}$$

Results and discussion

Zinc thiolates and dithiolates : Electrochemical reactions of thiophenol, butane-1-thiol, butane-1,4-dithiol, hexane-1,6-dithiol have been conducted at sacrificial zinc anode and inert platinum cathode. Elemental analysis (Zn, C and H) of the products isolated from the anode compartment reveals that the analytical data conform to $\text{Zn}(\text{SR})_2$ and $\text{ZnS}_2(\text{CH}_2)_n$. These products are insoluble in commonly used organic solvents like chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, acetone, methanol, benzene etc. Melting point determination of these products reveals that they do not melt upto 300°C. Some of these show a colour change.

The infrared spectral data of these products reveals that the characteristic bands appear in the region of 400–260 cm^{-1} and 660–650 cm^{-1} . However the band due to $\nu(\text{S-H})^{10}$ which generally appears around 2600–2550 cm^{-1} is missing in the infrared spectra of these products.

Survey of the literature^{11–15} reveals that $\nu(\text{M-S})$ stretching bands appears in the region of 400–250 cm^{-1} . The bands present in the region of 400–260 cm^{-1} are attributed to $\nu(\text{Zn-S})$ stretching vibration of bridged metal thiolate and dithiolate indicating the polymeric nature of these compounds. The bands, which are appearing in the region 650–660 cm^{-1} , are also in agreement with the $\nu(\text{C-S})$ stretching modes reported in literature¹². The insoluble behaviour of these compounds in various organic solvents also supports the polymeric nature of these compounds. The plausible structure of these compounds is given in Fig. 1.

Thus the infrared spectral data, solubility behavior and elemental analysis of the present products show that these are zinc thiolates/dithiolates formed by replacement of poly-

Fig. 1

tion of thiol/dithiol by anode zinc. The reaction scheme for formation of products is detailed below :

At cathode :

At anode :

Current efficiencies of some of these systems have also been determined which are quite close to 100% thereby indicating that the reactions leading to formation of these thiolates and dithiolates are the predominant reactions of these systems.

The coordination compounds of zinc thiolate and dithiolates : Zinc thiolates and dithiolates were refluxed with 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl in different solvents like benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, DMSO, diethylether etc. for more than 48 h. However, the elemental analysis shows that these donor molecules could not rupture the thiolate bridges in these compounds to form their coordination compounds. It was, therefore decided to add the ligand to these thiolates and dithiolates before these are polymerized. Therefore in addition to supporting electrolyte, 1.0 g of the ligand has also been added to these systems and the solution was electrolysed for 8 h. The solid product separated in anode compartment was filtered, washed with dry ether and dried under vacuum. The analytical data conform to $\text{Zn}(\text{SR})_2 \cdot \text{L}$ in case of thiol and $\text{ZnS}_2(\text{CH}_2)_n \cdot \text{L}$ in case of dithiol.

Survey of literature reveals that $\nu(\text{C} \equiv \text{N})$ in 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl appear around 1310–1360 cm^{-1} ¹⁰. It has been observed that in these complexes this band appear at 10–20 cm^{-1} higher than 1,10-phenanthroline

or 2,2'-bipyridyl. Infrared spectra of these compounds also exhibit peaks in the region of 420–265 cm^{-1} and 665–655 cm^{-1} . These bands are assigned to $\nu(\text{M-S})$ modes and $\nu(\text{C-S})$ modes^{11–15} respectively. Shift of these bands indicates that the ligand has been added to these systems. These coordinate compounds are also insoluble in commonly used organic solvents like benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, DMSO, diethylether etc. Thereby indicating that these could be polymeric in nature like their parent zinc thiolate/dithiolate.

Current efficiencies of some of these systems have also determined which are quite close to 100%, there by indicating that the reactions leading to formation of coordination compounds are the predominant reactions of these systems.

The project studies thus reveals that electrochemical method for synthesis of zinc thiolates, zinc dithiolates and their coordination compounds is a single step process and is quite simple as compared to other reported¹⁶ multi step methods for the synthesis of these compounds.

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